

Role Of Family Education Level In Access to Higher Education In India: A Comparative Analysis Of Non-Reserved And Scheduled Castes

Dr. Sahab Deen Rawat

Assistant Professor

School of Humanities, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab,
India

Abstract

The educational status of the family members plays an important role in access to education, especially higher education. Scheduled Castes is considered one of the most educationally backward communities in India. Educational backwardness is related to their socio-economic conditions internalized in the social structure of Indian society. The present article is an attempt to study the spatial analysis of the educational level and its role in attaining higher education in India. The paper is based on the quantitative exercise of primary data collected from eight states of India. Educational status of the family and accessibility to higher education has been computed for analysing the spatial pattern of higher education with the help of geo-spatial technology (GIS mapping). Analysis reveals that there is a very high variation in the educational level and accessibility to higher education among the Scheduled Castes and Non-Reserved Castes across India.

Keywords: *Accessibility, Educational-Status, Higher-Education (HE), India, Non-Reserved Castes (NRC), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Scheduled Castes (SC), Spatial Disparity.*

Introduction

Socio-economic factors play an important role in access to education, especially higher education. Education improves human capital through the process of gaining knowledge which is the basis of social capital. Moreover, education is an important mechanism for the process of social mobility (Blau & Duncan, 1967, and Breen, 2004); it transforms an under development society into rich social capital under the process of enhancing the merit of an

individual. Thus, socio-economic factors highly influence the progress of an individual member as well as a whole society. In the context of Indian society, factors like gender, caste, class, religion and economic conditions are important in determining the accessibility to higher education. The present paper is an attempt to analyze the role of the education level of the family in access to higher education. The socio-economic differences in terms of the education level of the family have been a comparison between non-reserved and scheduled castes the viewpoint of access to higher education. The paper has been divided into two sections i.e. the education level of the family and, accessibility to higher education. Thus, the paper is an attempt to analyze the role of the socio-economic condition in determining the accessibility of higher education for an individual in the family.

Data Source and Methodology

The present chapter is based on primary household data interviewed from villages in the study areas across India. There were total of 603 household samples have been collected representing the population of 40 villages from eight states in India. A composite index from different educational variables has been developed through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) score for particular educational issues in order to analyze the spatial disparity between Scheduled Castes and Non-Reserved Castes. The PCA method of index construction offers a technique that combines numerous components into one index so that the index will be as similar as possible with respect to all the component characteristics that were condensed into one or a few indexes. PCA reduces a large number of variables or indices a smaller number of conceptual variables. Computer package SPSS-20 provides a computation facility of Principal Component Analysis scores for given distribution (NUEPA, 2009).

Table1 Properties of PCA Composite Index for Scheduled Castes								
S L	PCA Index	KMO =0.6 Min.	BTS= p<0.05	CC = > 0.3 % & many	Eigenv alue = > 1	Scree Plot	Cmpnt. Explains	Cmpnt. Extracted
1	FEI	0.634	0.002	Many	4	>1	27.408	First
2	HEAI	0.335	0.017	Many	8	>1	14.375	First
Properties of PCA Composite Index for Non-Reserved								
S L	PCA Index	KMO =0.6 Min.	BTS= p<0.05	CC= > 0.3 % many	Eigen Value = > 1	Scree Plot	Cmpnt. Explains	Cmpnt. Extracted
1	FEI	0.571	0.023	Many	5	>1	18.161	First
2	HEAI	0.645	0.000	Many	5	>1	17.426	First

Note: **FEI**=Family Education Index,**HEAI**=Higher Education Accessibility Index

There are 603 household samples that have been utilized for analysis. This makes 40 different cases. So, 40 cases (N=40) with the different number of variables for separate PCA index have been mention in table 1. In this way, PCA composite indices have been constructed fulfilling the necessary conditions of Principal Component Analysis as mentioned in the above table 1.

Family Education Level

The family members having a higher level of education can increase children's ability to gain knowledge in a particular subject and make efficient in educational activities and, serve as a form of 'surrogate' or 'proximate' literacy (Foster and Rosenzweig, 1996). For measuring the family education level a *Family Education Index (FEI)* has been used to determine the educational status of the surveyed households.

Scheduled Castes

Education scenario of scheduled caste families reveals that the scheduled castes population having education of below primary, primary, junior high school, high school, higher secondary school, and diploma education shares 8%, 8%, 10%, 6% and 1% of the total population respectively. Furthermore,

the scheduled caste population having a graduation, post-graduation and Ph.D. level of education constitutes 11%, 3% and 0.08% of the total population respectively. The rest of the 45% scheduled caste population are either illiterate or perusing education or below the age of schooling (Appendix-1).

Map-1 Map-2

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

The spatial disparity in Family Education Index (FEI) shows that the district Kannur has recorded highest score with 2.36 followed by Thiruvananthapuram and Visakhapatnam; while on the other hand, Sitapur (-1.83) stand at the bottom level of educational development of scheduled castes preceded by Bijnor and Murshidabad (Map-1).

Non-Reserved Castes

Educational status of non-reserved families shows that the non-reserved population having an education of below primary, primary, Junior High school, high school, higher secondary school, and diploma education comprises 9%, 6%, 5%, 12%, 9% and 1% of the total population respectively. Moreover, non-reserved having graduation, post-graduation and Ph.D. level of education shares 22%, 10% and 0.47 % of the total population respectively. The rest of the 25% non-reserved population are either illiterate or perusing education or below the age of schooling (Appendix-2). The Family Education Index (FEI) of Non-reserved shows that the district Karimnagar has recorded the highest score with 2.41 followed by Alappuzha and Kalburagi; while, West Midnapore (-1.87) have the lowest level of educational development of Non-reserved castes preceded by Jalpaiguri and Samastipur (Map-2).

The proportion of the surveyed population having the primary, secondary and post-secondary level of education for scheduled castes constitutes 16%, 22% and 16% of the total population. On the other hand, the non-reserved population having the primary, secondary and post-secondary levels of education constitutes 15%, 26% and 35% of the total NS population. Thus, it is clear that non-reserved having a better position in family educational development in comparison to scheduled castes especially in the post-secondary level of education.

With the comparison of Map 1 and Map 2, a spatial pattern of family education reveals that most of the surveyed districts in northern India come

under lower levels of family education; while districts of southern India record higher levels of family education for both social groups.

In northern states, no districts come under the high-level family education index for both social groups. There were a total of 7 districts like Mathura, Jalpaiguri, and Alwar, etc. have recorded medium level; and the rest of the 13 districts Purulia, Araria, and Sitapur, etc. have a low level of family education index for scheduled castes. On the other hand in the case of non-reserved, 10 districts like Bikaner, Bijnor, and Murshidabad, etc. have recorded medium level; and 10 districts like Barmer, Sitapur, and West Midnapore etc. have registered low level of family education index. In cases of southern states, total 7 districts like Kannur, Thiruvananthapuram, and Visakhapatnam, etc. have recorded high level, 10 districts like Alappuzha, Mysore, and Pune, etc. recorded medium level and, 3 districts like Aurangabad and SPS Nellore, etc. have recorded low level of family education index for scheduled castes. In cases of non-reserved in southern states, 6 districts like Mallapuram, Davanagere, and Nalgonda, etc. recorded a high level, 13 districts like Kannur, Karwar, and Pune, etc. medium level and, only district of Latur has registered low level of family education index.

There were a total of 7 districts come under high level, 17 districts in medium level and 16 districts in the low level of family education for scheduled castes. On the other hand, a total of 6 districts come under high level, 23 districts in medium level and 11 districts in the low level of family education for Non-Reserved. Therefore, it may say that the total family education statuses of southern states are in a better position in comparison to northern states for both social groups. However, overall family education statuses of non-reserved are much better than scheduled castes in the study area.

Higher Education Accessibility

Higher education accessibility is the result of multiple factors like socio-economic, schooling achievement, educational environment of household, institutional and government policies, etc. greatly influence access to higher education. The father's education, mother's education, father's occupation, family income, and completion of school education are significantly and positively associated with enrolling in an advanced level of education (Tomul and Polat, 2013). Educational attainment of parents has a positive correlation with the attainment of their girl children. For assessment of higher education accessibility a composite index (*Higher Education Accessibility Index (HEAI)*) composition of enrollment rate in different disciplines and levels of higher education has been plotted on the map of study areas for each of the social groups.

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Scheduled Castes

The scheduled castes student who was enrolled in under-graduation of BA, B.Sc., B.Com, B.Tech/BE and, professional graduation/ additional professional graduation shares 23%, 4%, 7%, 2% and 6% of the total scheduled castes students respectively. The scheduled castes students who

were enrolled in post-graduation of MA, M.Sc, M.Com, and M.Tech and, professional post-graduation/ an additional professional post-graduation constitute 5%, 1%, 2%, 0.25% and 4% of the total scheduled castes students correspondingly. Scheduled castes students who were enrolled in M.Phil/Ph.D., perusing M.Phil/Ph.D., perusing graduation and perusing post-graduation comprises 0.25%, 0.74%, 25% and, 6% of the total students respectively. Overall 93% of Scheduled castes students have done/perusing their higher education in regular mode of education of the total students (Appendix-3).

Regarding scheduled castes' higher education accessibility, district Bengaluru Rural has recorded the highest HEAI score with 0.99 followed by Kannur and Rohtas; while on the other hand, Ajmer (-3.83) has registered lowest HEAI score preceded by Alwar and Bikaner. Map 3 shows that more or less uniform pattern of access to higher education in the study areas. Most of the district (34 out of 40) have recorded a good accessibility score (high and Medium level) across the study area. There are 15 districts like TVM, Aurangabad and West Champaran, etc. records high level; 19 districts like Mallapuram, Karimnagar, and Bijnor, etc. registers medium level and; rest of the 6 districts comes under low level of HEAI score. However, overall southern states are slightly better than the northern states. Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, West Bengal, and Uttar Pradesh are the best, Kerala, Karnataka and Bihar is better and Rajasthan is slightly low.

Non-Reserved Castes

The non-reserved student who was enrolled in under-graduation of BA, B.Sc., B.Com, B.Tech/BE and, professional graduation/ additional professional graduation shares 22%, 6%, 9%, 10% and 10% of the total non-reserved students respectively. The non-reserved students who were enrolled in post-graduation of MA, M.Sc., M.Com, and M.Tech and, professional post-graduation/ an additional professional post-graduation constitute 11%, 7%,

5%, 6% and 13% of the total non-reserved students correspondingly. The non-reserved students who were enrolled in M.Phil/Ph.D. and have done their higher education in regular mode of education 3% and 99% of the total students respectively (Appendix-4).

Concerning higher education accessibility for non-reserved, district Alwar has recorded the highest HEAI score with 1.13 followed by Davanagere and Kalburagi; while on the other hand, South 24 Parganas (-3.73) stand at bottom level preceded by Ajmer and Sitapur. Map 4 display a more or less uniform pattern of access to higher education in the study areas. The majority of the districts (36 out of 40) have recorded a good accessibility score (high and Medium level) across the study area. There are 20 districts like Karwar, Nalgonda, and Bikaner, etc. show a high level; 16 districts like Ernakulam, Udaipur, and Jalpaiguri, etc. registers medium level and; rest of the 4 districts comes under low level of HEAI score. However, overall southern states are slightly better than the northern states. Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, and Maharashtra are the best; Kerala and Rajasthan are better; Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal slightly less good.

Discussion

Analysis of the educational status of the family and its role in access to higher education reveals that overall proportions of Non-Reserved Castes are much better than Scheduled Castes in all the selected variables of educational level of the families and accessibility to higher education except enrollment in BA courses for Scheduled Castes; which indicates scheduled castes students have high tendency to enroll in social sciences and humanities in higher education due to their weak social and economic background. Since family education level determines the students' educational attainment which reflects in the form of portion to admitted student in a college (Donoso and Schiefelbein, 2003).

A comparison between the map 3 and map4 of accessibility to higher education show an approximately uniform pattern of access to higher education for both the social groups in the study area. However, overall southern states are slightly better than northern states for both the social groups. Nonetheless, the states, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, West Bengal and Uttar Pradesh showing a much better position for Scheduled castes; and Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and Maharashtra have a quite good position for non-reserved castes accessibility to higher education.

From the above debate, it is noted that although both the social groups have good accessibility to higher education. Nonetheless, scheduled castes have comparatively lower accessibility to higher education than the Non-Reserved. Besides, scheduled castes have a higher tendency to enroll in social sciences and humanities in higher education. The spatial pattern shows that access to higher education varies from state to state differently for scheduled castes and Non-Reserved. Nevertheless, southern India is better than northern India in access to high education for the social groups.

Conclusion

Generally, southern states having a comparatively better status in most of the aspects of educational achievement and social and economic conditions for both the social groups with few exceptions. Nonetheless, district level status varies from state to state differently for scheduled castes as well as Non-Reserved. The scheduled castes are considered one of the most backward segments of our society, which is evidently verified true in the light of primary data in terms of comparative analysis of educational achievement and another socio-economic status between Scheduled castes and Non-Reserved castes. Normally, non-reserved household leads in family education level and accessibility to higher education.

Thus, it can be stated that the accessibility to higher education influenced by multiple factors of the social and economic conditions along with many others. These facts also have been proved through analysis indicating comparatively lower enrollment and performance in higher education for scheduled castes. That is why; scheduled castes are relatively unable to achieve the expected level of higher education and lead a successful life, despite the fact that having a reservation in higher education along with numbers of supplementary social welfare policies and programs initiated by the government. On the other hand, non-reserved are able to achieve success in higher education and leads a fairly successful life without having a reservation, because of their strong social and economic background.

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Appendix

Appendix-1 Education Level of Scheduled Castes Family (%)						
SL	District	Literate < Primary	Primary	JHS	High School	HSS
1	Ernakulam	2.04	14.29	0.00	22.45	10.20
2	Thiruvananthapuram	11.36	2.27	0.00	34.09	9.09
3	Alappuzha	4.35	19.57	4.35	19.57	4.35
4	Mallapuram	0.00	10.00	2.00	20.00	12.00
5	Kannur	3.64	5.45	0.00	27.27	10.91
6	Mysore	5.88	5.88	1.47	20.59	1.47
7	Bengaluru Rural	8.33	4.17	1.39	18.06	8.33
8	Uttara Kannada	6.00	14.00	10.00	14.00	10.00
9	Davanagere	1.85	16.67	0.00	14.81	7.41
10	Kalburagi	3.51	1.75	0.00	3.51	7.02
11	Anantapur	8.77	7.02	0.00	5.26	7.02
12	SPS Nellore	4.55	6.82	11.36	2.27	4.55
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	5.26	0.00	15.79	2.63
14	Nalgonda	7.02	3.51	3.51	7.02	0.00
15	Karimnagar	1.92	1.92	1.92	17.31	15.38
16	Nagpur	1.96	1.96	3.92	13.73	3.92
17	Latur	0.00	21.15	3.85	7.69	13.46
18	Kolhapur	3.77	18.87	7.55	13.21	5.66
19	Pune	3.70	16.67	9.26	14.81	5.56
20	Aurangabad	8.77	12.28	3.51	8.77	0.00
21	Udaipur	16.67	10.71	5.95	10.71	7.14
22	Barmer	5.97	16.42	7.46	5.97	13.43
23	Bikaner	11.00	12.00	10.00	7.00	4.00
24	Ajmer	2.82	8.45	7.04	7.04	2.82
25	Alwar	18.31	4.23	5.63	7.04	5.63
26	Purulia	7.69	3.85	9.62	5.77	3.85
27	W. Medinapor	5.45	21.82	1.82	3.64	0.00
28	S.24 Parganas	7.58	6.06	7.58	10.61	4.55
29	Murshidabad	0.00	8.00	8.00	6.00	0.00
30	Jalpaiguri	7.84	5.88	3.92	9.80	5.88
31	Araria	13.33	9.33	8.00	4.00	2.67
32	Banka	9.21	2.63	10.53	5.26	6.58
33	Samastipur	8.96	0.00	5.97	4.48	2.99
34	W. Champaran	22.35	9.41	5.88	7.06	7.06
35	Rohtas	14.67	4.00	2.67	5.33	5.33
36	Gorakhpur	6.78	8.47	5.08	11.86	8.47
37	Sonbhadra	2.78	11.11	8.33	1.39	6.94
38	Sitapur	9.88	3.70	16.05	4.94	0.00
39	Bijnor	7.87	2.25	15.73	4.49	4.49
40	Mathura	11.90	2.38	8.33	3.57	7.14
41	Total	7.71	8.23	5.90	9.92	5.82

Appendix-1					
Education Level of Scheduled Castes Family (%)					
SL	District	Diploma/ Certificate	Graduate	Post-Graduate	M.Phil./PHD
1	Ernakulam	0.00	16.33	14.29	0.00
2	Thiruvananthapuram	2.27	25.00	4.55	0.00
3	Alappuzha	2.17	15.22	4.35	2.17
4	Mallapuram	0.00	12.00	0.00	2.00
5	Kannur	3.64	23.64	1.82	0.00
6	Mysore	1.47	7.35	2.94	0.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	2.78	13.89	1.39	0.00
8	Uttara Kannada	10.00	2.00	0.00	0.00
9	Davanagere	3.70	12.96	1.85	0.00
10	Kalburagi	1.75	10.53	10.53	0.00
11	Anantapur	5.26	8.77	3.51	0.00
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	13.64	0.00	0.00
13	Visakhapatnam	7.89	15.79	0.00	0.00
14	Nalgonda	0.00	21.05	14.04	0.00
15	Karimnagar	3.85	11.54	1.92	0.00
16	Nagpur	1.96	5.88	0.00	0.00
17	Latur	1.92	1.92	3.85	0.00
18	Kolhapur	1.89	11.32	1.89	0.00
19	Pune	0.00	12.96	0.00	0.00
20	Aurangabad	0.00	3.51	3.51	0.00
21	Udaipur	0.00	11.90	10.71	0.00
22	Barmer	1.49	5.97	2.99	0.00
23	Bikaner	0.00	9.00	3.00	0.00
24	Ajmer	2.82	12.68	5.63	0.00
25	Alwar	0.00	15.49	4.23	0.00
26	Purulia	0.00	3.85	0.00	0.00
27	W. Medinapor	0.00	5.45	1.82	0.00
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	13.64	1.52	0.00
29	Murshidabad	0.00	2.00	2.00	0.00
30	Jalpaiguri	0.00	11.76	1.96	0.00
31	Araria	0.00	14.67	0.00	0.00
32	Banka	1.32	6.58	0.00	0.00
33	Samastipur	0.00	13.43	4.48	0.00
34	W. Champaran	0.00	10.59	0.00	0.00
35	Rohtas	0.00	18.67	0.00	0.00
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	10.17	5.08	0.00
37	Sonbhadra	1.39	9.72	4.17	0.00
38	Sitapur	0.00	4.94	3.70	0.00
39	Bijnor	0.00	8.99	2.25	0.00
40	Mathura	1.19	15.48	2.38	0.00
41	Total	1.29	11.16	3.17	0.08

Appendix-2						
Education Level of Non-Reserved Family (%)						
SL	District	Literate < Primary	Primary	JHS	High School	HSS
1	Ernakulam	0.00	0.00	0.00	21.05	5.26
2	Thiruvananthapuram	12.50	12.50	0.00	12.50	4.17
3	Alappuzha	4.17	0.00	0.00	16.67	16.67
4	Mallapuram	4.00	4.00	0.00	20.00	16.00
5	Kannur	6.67	3.33	3.33	20.00	6.67
6	Mysore	0.00	5.26	0.00	5.26	0.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	15.38	3.85	0.00	3.85	11.54
8	Uttara Kannada	6.25	0.00	3.13	12.50	15.63
9	Davanagere	8.57	2.86	2.86	31.43	11.43
10	Kalburagi	12.90	12.90	0.00	12.90	6.45
11	Anantapur	0.00	30.43	0.00	4.35	0.00
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	0.00	0.00	22.73	13.64
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	4.76	4.76	33.33	0.00
14	Nalgonda	3.45	10.34	0.00	10.34	13.79
15	Karimnagar	0.00	7.69	0.00	11.54	3.85
16	Nagpur	3.03	12.12	0.00	6.06	15.15
17	Latur	11.76	5.88	8.82	26.47	5.88
18	Kolhapur	0.00	4.35	0.00	13.04	13.04
19	Pune	0.00	5.71	0.00	5.71	11.43
20	Aurangabad	6.45	3.23	6.45	19.35	19.35
21	Udaipur	10.26	7.69	7.69	12.82	5.13
22	Barmer	5.88	5.88	14.71	8.82	8.82
23	Bikaner	0.00	0.00	0.00	8.82	8.82
24	Ajmer	12.12	12.12	6.06	6.06	6.06
25	Alwar	12.00	0.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
26	Purulia	5.71	0.00	11.43	20.00	5.71
27	W. Medinapor	7.14	7.14	17.86	7.14	3.57
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	0.00	10.53	10.53	15.79
29	Murshidabad	0.00	12.00	8.00	4.00	12.00
30	Jalpaiguri	12.50	3.13	15.63	12.50	9.38
31	Araria	14.29	7.14	4.76	14.29	9.52
32	Banka	3.23	0.00	9.68	6.45	6.45
33	Samastipur	17.65	0.00	8.82	11.76	8.82
34	W.Champaran	18.42	0.00	2.63	10.53	5.26
35	Rohtas	17.50	5.00	2.50	12.50	7.50
36	Gorakhpur	16.28	9.30	4.65	0.00	16.28
37	Sonbhadra	15.71	2.86	5.71	7.14	14.29
38	Sitapur	8.57	5.71	8.57	5.71	11.43
39	Bijnor	14.00	12.00	2.00	10.00	6.00
40	Mathura	17.54	3.51	5.26	5.26	10.53
41	Total	8.86	5.52	4.74	11.66	9.41

Appendix-2					
Education Level of Non-Reserved Family (%)					
SL	District	Diploma/ Certificate	Graduate	Post-Graduate	M.Phil./PHD
1	Ernakulam	5.26	36.84	21.05	0.00
2	Thiruvananthapuram	0.00	29.17	4.17	0.00
3	Alappuzha	8.33	33.33	8.33	0.00
4	Mallapuram	0.00	24.00	20.00	0.00
5	Kannur	0.00	23.33	16.67	0.00
6	Mysore	0.00	36.84	21.05	0.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	0.00	23.08	30.77	0.00
8	Uttara Kannada	0.00	28.13	9.38	0.00
9	Davanagere	2.86	11.43	8.57	0.00
10	Kalburagi	0.00	9.68	12.90	3.23
11	Anantapur	4.35	21.74	21.74	0.00
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	36.36	0.00	4.55
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	23.81	9.52	0.00
14	Nalgonda	3.45	20.69	10.34	0.00
15	Karimnagar	7.69	19.23	15.38	0.00
16	Nagpur	0.00	24.24	9.09	0.00
17	Latur	0.00	14.71	8.82	0.00
18	Kolhapur	0.00	34.78	4.35	0.00
19	Pune	0.00	22.86	8.57	2.86
20	Aurangabad	3.23	16.13	3.23	0.00
21	Udaipur	0.00	17.95	12.82	2.56
22	Barmer	0.00	14.71	0.00	0.00
23	Bikaner	0.00	29.41	23.53	0.00
24	Ajmer	3.03	21.21	3.03	3.03
25	Alwar	0.00	28.00	40.00	0.00
26	Purulia	0.00	28.57	2.86	0.00
27	W. Medinapor	0.00	25.00	7.14	0.00
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	10.53	21.05	0.00
29	Murshidabad	0.00	24.00	16.00	0.00
30	Jalpaiguri	0.00	28.13	0.00	0.00
31	Araria	2.38	19.05	2.38	0.00
32	Banka	0.00	41.94	16.13	0.00
33	Samastipur	0.00	44.12	0.00	0.00
34	W. Champaran	0.00	13.16	15.79	0.00
35	Rohtas	2.50	30.00	0.00	0.00
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	20.93	9.30	0.00
37	Sonbhadra	4.29	8.57	12.86	1.43
38	Sitapur	0.00	14.29	14.29	0.00
39	Bijnor	0.00	4.00	8.00	0.00
40	Mathura	3.51	28.07	3.51	0.00
	Total	1.32	22.40	10.50	0.47

Appendix-3									
Accessibility to Higher Education for Scheduled Castes (%)									
SL	District	BA	B.Sc.	B.Com	B.Tech	Professional Graduation (+Professional)	MA	M.Sc.	M.Com
1	Ernakulam	9.09	0.00	9.09	0.00	9.09	9.09	0.00	9.09
2	Thiruvananthapuram	20.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
3	Alappuzha	36.36	9.09	9.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
4	Mallapuram	10.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	Kannur	20.00	10.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00
6	Mysore	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	30.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00
8	Uttara Kannada	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
9	Davanagere	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	10.00
10	Kalburagi	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	Anantapur	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
12	SPS Nellore	10.00	10.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	10.00	10.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	Nalgonda	20.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	20.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
15	Karimnagar	0.00	0.00	20.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
16	Nagpur	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
17	Latur	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
18	Kolhapur	30.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
19	Pune	10.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20	Aurangabad	0.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00
21	Udaipur	20.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	20.00
22	Barmer	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
23	Bikaner	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
24	Ajmer	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
25	Alwar	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
26	Purulia	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
27	W. Medinapor	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
28	S.24 Parganas	30.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
29	Murshidabad	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
30	Jalpaiguri	20.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
31	Araria	70.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
32	Banka	20.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
33	Samastipur	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00
34	W. Champaran	60.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00
35	Rohtas	40.00	10.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
36	Gorakhpur	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
37	Sonbhadra	9.09	0.00	18.18	0.00	9.09	0.00	0.00	0.00
38	Sitapur	20.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00
39	Bijnor	50.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
40	Mathura	50.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Total	22.58	3.97	7.20	2.23	5.46	4.71	0.99	2.23

Appendix-3 Accessibility to Higher Education for Scheduled Castes (%)								
S L	District	M.Tech	PG (+Prof.)	Ph.D./ M.Phil	Graduation Perusing	PG Perusing	Ph.D. Perusing	The regular mode of Education
1	Ernakulam	0.00	18.18	0.00	9.09	0.00	0.00	100.00
2	Thiruvananthapuram	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
3	Alappuzha	0.00	0.00	0.00	18.18	0.00	0.00	100.00
4	Mallapuram	0.00	0.00	10.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
5	Kannur	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
6	Mysore	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	80.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
8	Uttara Kannada	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
9	Davanagere	0.00	10.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	80.00
10	Kalburagi	0.00	20.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	20.00	100.00
11	Anantapur	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
14	Nalgonda	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
15	Karimnagar	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
16	Nagpur	0.00	0.00	0.00	50.00	0.00	0.00	90.00
17	Latur	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.00	10.00	0.00	100.00
18	Kolhapur	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	90.00
19	Pune	0.00	0.00	0.00	50.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
20	Aurangabad	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
21	Udaipur	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	80.00
22	Barmer	0.00	20.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
23	Bikaner	0.00	20.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	90.00
24	Ajmer	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	40.00
25	Alwar	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	70.00
26	Purulia	0.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	10.00	0.00	100.00
27	W. Medinapor	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.00	10.00	0.00	90.00
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	10.00	0.00	100.00
29	Murshidabad	0.00	10.00	0.00	70.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
30	Jalpaiguri	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	10.00	0.00	80.00
31	Araria	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	70.00
32	Banka	0.00	0.00	0.00	50.00	0.00	0.00	90.00
33	Samastipur	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	30.00	0.00	100.00
34	W. Champaran	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	10.00	0.00	100.00
35	Rohtas	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
37	Sonbhadra	0.00	9.09	0.00	36.36	18.18	0.00	100.00
38	Sitapur	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	90.00
39	Bijnor	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	10.00	0.00	90.00
40	Mathura	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
	Total	0.25	3.97	0.25	24.57	5.46	0.74	93.30

Appendix-4 Accessibility to Higher Education for Non-Reserved Castes (%)								
SL	District	BA	B.Sc.	B.Com	B.Tech./ BE	Graduation (Professional/ +Professional)	MA	M.Sc.
1	Ernakulam	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	20.00	0.00
2	Thiruvananthapuram	60.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00
3	Alappuzha	20.00	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
4	Mallapuram	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	20.00	20.00
5	Kannur	20.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	Mysore	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	20.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00
8	Uttara Kannada	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	20.00
9	Davanagere	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
10	Kalburagi	20.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	Anantapur	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	0.00	20.00	60.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	Nalgonda	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
15	Karimnagar	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
16	Nagpur	0.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
17	Latur	20.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
18	Kolhapur	40.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
19	Pune	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20	Aurangabad	20.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
21	Udaipur	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00
22	Barmer	40.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	0.00
23	Bikaner	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
24	Ajmer	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	20.00	20.00	0.00
25	Alwar	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00
26	Purulia	40.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	20.00
27	W. Medinapor	40.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00
28	S.24 Parganas	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	80.00	0.00
29	Murshidabad	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	40.00
30	Jalpaiguri	80.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
31	Araria	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00
32	Banka	60.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
33	Samastipur	80.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
34	W. Champaran	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00
35	Rohtas	40.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00
36	Gorakhpur	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00
37	Sonbhadra	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00
38	Sitapur	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00
39	Bijnor	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.00
40	Mathura	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	60.00	0.00	20.00
	Total	21.50	6.00	9.00	9.50	9.50	11.00	6.50

Appendix-4 Accessibility to Higher Education for Non-Reserved Castes (%)						
SL	District	M.Com	M.Tech.	PG (Professional/ +Professional)	Ph.D.	The regular mode of Education
1	Ernakulam	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
2	Thiruvananthapuram	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
3	Alappuzha	20.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
4	Mallapuram	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
5	Kannur	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
6	Mysore	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
7	Bengaluru Rural	0.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	100.00
8	Uttara Kannada	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
9	Davanagere	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	100.00
10	Kalburagi	0.00	0.00	40.00	20.00	100.00
11	Anantapur	0.00	40.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	100.00
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
14	Nalgonda	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	100.00
15	Karimnagar	20.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
16	Nagpur	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	100.00
17	Latur	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	100.00
18	Kolhapur	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
19	Pune	40.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	100.00
20	Aurangabad	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
21	Udaipur	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	100.00
22	Barmer	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
23	Bikaner	60.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
24	Ajmer	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	80.00
25	Alwar	0.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	100.00
26	Purulia	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
27	W. Medinapor	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	80.00
29	Murshidabad	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
30	Jalpaiguri	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
31	Araria	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
32	Banka	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
33	Samastipur	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
34	W. Champaran	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
35	Rohtas	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
37	Sonbhadra	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
38	Sitapur	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
39	Bijnor	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	100.00
40	Mathura	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
	Total	5.00	5.50	13.00	2.50	99.00